

Title: Creating educational commons' spaces *hand-in-hand* with children

Abstract:

Intersectional and intergenerational collaboration is essential to develop and accelerate the potential impact of commons in Education, aiming in reducing inequalities and promoting the active social inclusion of children and young people.

Although the perspective of the adults frequently dominates the new field of educational and pedagogical commons (Pechtelidis&Kioupkiolis, 2020), it is our aim to bring empirical inquiries into the views and perceptions of children as commoners, but also commoning practices and community and common good, presenting two research-action projects carried out in the north of Portugal by the UMinho SMOOTH team: Children's Club and Children's Advisory Board.

Despite children's vulnerable living conditions, with scarce material resources both in the community and at school, and academic performance difficulties showing indiscipline and precarious behaviours with regard to health and well-being, we will be presenting the several steps that have been taken in the two projects.

By describing and analysing the different strategies we developed with children during the research process, the goal is to show how, in a collective way, all the members of the educational community, founded in the principles of equality, freedom and participation, enrolled on these dynamics and built common practices.

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